

EFFECT OF PERTURBATIONS ON ORBITAL DENSITY USING EULERIAN ORBIT DYNAMICS

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The behavior of object density after a fragmentation has been analyzed using “Eulerian orbit dynamics”, our term for the propagation of densities, rather than points. We previously pioneered a technique that propagates the spatial density of orbital objects exactly. In the present work, we show the effects of the J_2 gravitational perturbation on the density evolution from a low-earth orbit fragmentation. The fractional change in density due to the perturbation averages on the order of a tenth of a percent.

INTRODUCTION

In previous publications [1, 2, 3], we have shown how to compute the exact spatial density of debris after a fragmentation. The technique we use, which we call Housen’s method, is to use the transformation of variables technique from calculus and the complete Lambert solution, that is, the solution of the two-point boundary value problem for orbital motion over all possible routes between the fragmentation point and the point at which the density is to be evaluated. See [3] for more details. We call this technique “Eulerian orbit dynamics”, borrowing a term from fluid mechanics, to contrast it with traditional ephemeris propagation, playing the role of Lagrangian dynamics. There are noted features of the spatial distribution from a fragmentation that are independent of the initial velocity distribution, such as the pinch points, density bands which move away from the earth on the opposite side, and an antipodal line of high density.

In this paper, we introduce the J_2 gravitational perturbation into the solution, and examine the effect on the spatial density distribution for the fragmentation from a low-earth orbiting satellite at a few hours after the fragmentation.

PERTURBED TWO-POINT BOUNDARY SOLUTION

In previous work [1, 2, 3], we have shown the effects of two-body motion on various velocity distributions from a point source, such as what might happen in a fragmentation occurring over a period of time which is very small compared to the orbital period of the fragmenting object. A core part of this calculation is the solution to the complete Lambert problem at each point in space, meaning that all routes from the fragmentation point r_1 to the point in space r_2 at a later time

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must be solved. There are two mathematical solutions to the Lambert, or two-point point boundary, problem, for $N = 0$ and generally four solutions for $N > 0$, where N is the number of complete orbits made over the elapsed time. There is a maximum value of N based on the elapsed time and terminal points r_1 and r_2 , and for that maximum value, the final N may have only two solutions. The *complete* Lambert problem is the entire set of these solutions through the maximum possible value of N .

Once all the mathematical solutions have been determined, the non-physical solutions, those routes whose trajectories intersect the earth, must be eliminated. This can only be done once each route, or Lambert *mode*, has been solved. What remains is a set of modes, each of which has a distinct initial velocity vector, which will bring an object from the initial terminal point r_1 to the final point r_2 in the specified elapsed time. The spatial density is obtained by summing over the value of the velocity density divided by the absolute value of Jacobian determinant of the function mapping the initial velocity to the final position for these points. For two-body propagation, the formula for this Jacobian is available in the literature, for example, Arora et al. [4]

Since a force model is involved in both these calculations, computing the perturbed density flow requires at least that the two-point boundary value problem, or “perturbed Lambert problem” be solved. The most common methods of solving two-point boundary value problems are those in the *shooting method* family*, which converts the boundary value problem into an initial problem. Essentially, an initial value is picked, the point propagated, and the end point evaluated. An iteration is performed with successively improved initial values to end closer to the desired final value. If the partial derivatives of the final point with respect to the initial are available, the Jacobian matrix may be used to apply a multivariate Newton’s method, or differential correction, greatly improving the convergence.

For the problem at hand, we chose to use the shooting method described by Woollands et al. [5] in which, for the *particular solution solver*, the Jacobian matrix is computed numerically by propagating points displaced a small amount in velocity space on each Cartesian axis. This, combined with the iteration results in numerous propagations, typically around 100 at an elapsed time of four hours, to evaluate a single point. As the elapsed time increases, this number increases. A perturbed propagator must be used; in our case, we use a variable step integrator described by Shampine and Gordon and implemented by Montenbruck and Gill [6]. This propagator can model the common major forces, but it has no frame rotations, as for example for equinox precession, so it is “true of epoch”, or quasi-inertial, instead of truly inertial. That simplification results in an inaccuracy unimportant for the present calculation.

The initial value used for the shooting method implementation is the two-body solution. This solution is obtained with the iterated versine solution technique described and implemented by Russell [7]. This implementation, which uses a table lookup and biquintic interpolation, was found to be a great improvement in speed and accuracy over the Battin hypergeometric method we previously used [3]. However, the computation of density for each r_2 point with a perturbed model is substantially slower than the two-body solution. Most of the perturbation calculations were performed on the high-performance class computer that the Spacecraft Engineering Division of the Naval Research Laboratory recently acquired. This computer has 32 nodes of 48 CPU cores each, for a total of 1536 cores.

Because the perturbed Lambert iteration may not converge and because the variable step integra-

*https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Shooting_method

tion may not meet accuracy tolerance requirements, obtaining an accurate density at any given point and elapsed time is not guaranteed. Iteration failures, or anomalies, are identified in one of four categories: singularity or near-singularity of the Jacobian matrix (absolute value of determinant less than 1×10^{-10}), exceeding the iteration count limit (set to 100), maximum error in r_2 , and failure to converge (error in r_2 is larger than the error from each of the previous three iterations). The error in r_2 is computed by propagating the obtained initial velocity and finding the Cartesian distance between the resultant position vector and the target vector. The check for maximum error was disabled as it was found the other checks captured those errors. The iteration limit will capture all errors if there is no convergence failure check, but having the latter results in a substantial savings of computation time. Counts of anomalies obtained in the simulation are addressed in the “Results” section.

In our implementation, there are two simplifications taken. First, the Jacobian determinant is computed analytically from the two body propagation rather than the perturbation. The two-body propagation is also used for the earth intersection calculation so that only physical solutions are retained. While it is felt that anomalies are sufficiently limited in earlier times to be acceptable for the results presented, they do grow in number with elapsed time. One possible technique to avoid these anomalies is the direct multiple shooting method[†] that splits the time interval up into smaller segments. Another is to obtain a better initial velocity vector by subdividing the perturbation parameter values, such as the value of J_2 . However, neither of these methods were applied in the present study.

One way to improve the speed of the computation we contemplate is the use of an analytic propagator such as SGP4-XP.[‡] While there would be a notable loss of accuracy in using such a model, it is felt that it would be sufficiently accurate for our purposes.

FRAGMENTATION MODEL AND COMPARISON

A satellite in a circular, equatorial orbit at an altitude of 900 km is modeled with a fragmentation on the vernal equinox. The fragmentation has a relative velocity vector with a normal distribution that is isotropic with a standard deviation magnitude of 250 m s^{-1} and a mean of zero. The grid of evaluation is in the equatorial plane, between $-38\,280 \text{ km}$ and 7800 km with 24 km steps on the vernal equinox axis, between $-12\,960 \text{ km}$ and $12\,960 \text{ km}$ with 24 km steps in the perpendicular equatorial axis. The elapsed times evaluated are at one hour intervals from one through sixteen hours.

RESULTS

The results of the J_2 calculation of density are plotted separately every two hours for sixteen hours in fig. 2. In contrast, the same density for two-body motion is shown in fig. 1. They show, as expected, a very similar pattern to the unperturbed results. The pinch point and rings are clearly visible in both. In the figures, the density is plotted on a “zerolog” scale, where any density less than a minimum threshold of $1 \times 10^{-14} \text{ km}^{-3}$ is shown in black, and the densities above this threshold shown on a logarithmic scale that ranges from deep blue to white at a density above $5 \times 10^{-10} \text{ km}^{-3}$. The maximum densities are on the order of -9 km^{-3} . The green dot shows the location of the satellite “ghost” where the satellite would be had there been no fragmentation. Note the earth image is

[†]https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Direct_multiple_shooting_method

[‡]<https://www.space-track.org/documentation#/sgp4>

Figure 1: Density with two-body motion every two hours to sixteen hours

Figure 2: Density with J_2 perturbation every two hours to sixteen hours

Figure 3: Difference between the density from J_2 perturbation and two-body motion

Time (h)	RMS (km ⁻³)	Fraction
1	3.31131×10^{-10}	0.000406
2	2.01352×10^{-10}	0.000687
3	1.94658×10^{-10}	0.000566
4	2.1493×10^{-9}	0.003409
5	6.23561×10^{-10}	0.001638
6	6.487×10^{-10}	0.001668
7	3.25803×10^{-10}	0.001132
8	2.81203×10^{-10}	0.000882
9	4.79154×10^{-10}	0.001294
10	4.93766×10^{-10}	0.001842
11	3.69924×10^{-10}	0.001237
12	5.81783×10^{-10}	0.001839
13	3.66669×10^{-10}	0.001452
14	2.99139×10^{-10}	0.001342
15	1.05141×10^{-10}	0.000669
16	1.36664×10^{-10}	0.001002

Table 1: Effect of perturbations

Time (hr)	Number points	Pct points	Iteration	Convergence
1	2	1.08×10^{-4}	0	2
2	3	1.62×10^{-4}	4	0
3	61	3.29×10^{-3}	85	6
4	135	7.29×10^{-3}	183	10
5	301	0.0221	409	21
6	552	0.0298	651	101
7	1008	0.0544	1131	307
8	1664	0.0898	1553	729
9	2812	0.152	2035	1775
10	5198	0.281	2722	4324
11	9537	0.515	3535	9296
12	18357	0.991	4223	20470
13	32486	1.75	5678	39128
14	57125	3.08	7223	73241
15	95813	5.17	9208	130574
16	149744	8.09	11311	219044

Table 2: Anomalies in the Lambert particular solution, of evaluated r_2 points

Figure 4: Anomalies

symbolic and not oriented correctly for this orbit.

In fig. 3, the difference between the J_2 and two-body results are plotted every two hours on a linear scale. In these plots, red indicates greater density for the perturbation, yellow the same, and green less, gray are anomaly points, and black shows points where both values are close to zero ($< 0.5 \times 10^{-14} \text{ km}^{-3}$). For the later times, the upper left part of the bands show the most additional density from the perturbation and the inner rings show the greatest depletion.

A single number can serve as a summary showing how the density changes over the whole plane by computing the root mean square (RMS) difference between the densities of the two force models over all space,

$$\text{RMS} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (d_{J_2}(\mathbf{r}_i) - d_{\text{two-body}}(\mathbf{r}_i))^2} \quad (1)$$

for $N = 1851704$ points. The RMS values are given in table 1 along with the ratio of that RMS to the mean perturbed density over the plane. This table shows that the fractional effect of the J_2 perturbation is at most a few tenths of a percent. These statistics exclude points with anomalies.

The number of points (out of 1851704 points total) with anomalies in the particular solution solver are shown in table 2. The percent of anomalies are shown in the second column. The last two columns show the number of solutions where the iteration limit (100) was reached, and convergence failures. These two columns do not generally add up to the number of points affected because each point consists of multiple Lambert modes and thus the possibility of more than one mode for a given point exhibiting an anomaly. Up to twelve hours, less than one percent of points are affected, but the number of grows rapidly after that. It is interesting that through nine hours, the iteration limit dominates, and after that it shifts to the convergence failure, meaning that the r_2 error is rising instead of falling.

The location of points with anomalies are shown in fig. 4 in yellow for eight and ten through sixteen hours for each hour. The black represents points that have no anomalies and evaluate to zero density; the gray represent points that have no anomalies and evaluate to non-zero density. It is understandable that the area near the pinch point has a lot of anomalies. In addition, the outer edge of the antipodal bands have a small ridge of anomalies. There are two radial lines of points with anomalies, almost mirror images, near the pinch point, which is a curious phenomenon.

CONCLUSION

Using Eulerian orbit dynamics, the spatial density from the fragmentation of a low-earth orbit is computed with both a two-body force model and the J_2 gravitational perturbation with a normally distributed isotropic fragmentation with a standard deviation of relative velocity of 250 m s^{-1} . In the source orbital plane, the fractional density difference varies from 0.04% to 0.34% over one to sixteen hours of elapsed time.

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